

**COMMUNICATION CULTURE AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS IN
MODERN SOCIETY**

Teacher **Egamberdiyeva Iroda**

Student **Gulomova Zebo**

Student **Madaminova Muslima**

Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

ABSTRACT

In modern society the culture of communication should be considered as a complex individual education, acquired strengthened oath developed under the influence of various factors: subjective (will, temperament, cognitive characteristics, etc.), objective (environmental conditions), the identity of the individual, the teacher, the content, forms oath methods of teaching); representing the unity of different approaches and components, the degree to which the student understands the need and importance of communication culture as a common value, the level of mastery of basic skills of effective interaction with the process and its results, the level of knowledge effective communication techniques , is characterized by a degree of satisfaction.

Keywords : culture communication, methods, universal values, modern society.

INTRODUCTION

of society basis organize doer and this the most stable transitions possible has been the most important of values one this known one cultural in the environment which develops

One of the main components of culture is education. In modern society communication culture personal integrated quality being his indispensable part just information transmission system it's not, perhaps communication organize achieve knowledge including differentiation, integration, etc. At the same time,

modern in society cross-cultural communication done increase methods one as the interaction of language, thought and culture in the context of bilingualism or multilingualism effect is implied [6].

MAIN PART

Communication, like any philosophical, social, psychological and pedagogical process culture also includes a number of functions, one of the most important of which is this is a normative function.

At present, communication culture creates the necessary conditions for human development to himself special cases, relations and behavior work to be released environment forms, each one person grow up grown up at the time socialize. Adult reached In life, people follow developed cultural skills and use them in new ways to posterity spend So, modern in society communication culture a person an integral part of life, she is a person arrange life does.

Har one society (and sometimes his separately social groups) of communication develops certain regulatory principles, they are not only accepted by him done behavior in the standards strengthened, perhaps more or less To the right have has been in people too is brought up. This communication of culture she is or this gives reason to emphasize the existence of the level. Here culture is more than communication wider concept that we emphasize she is people collected all material and includes spiritual values [1]. At the same time, culture is a human activity describing methods, features of society's activity and its existence without them possible didn't happen shapes, styles and norms scope own into takes That's it to talk about the culture of production, recreation, communication with attitude can this with "culture" of the concept wide the meaning provides in this culture a person in their relationship norms and them done increase methods own into takes But culture of understanding narrower meaning too there is she is to the communication skills of people created and accepted in a particular society ownership level with is determined [3].

Thus, the culture of communication - as specific communication standards people between relationships norms, methods, forms is a set. From this except communication culture formation moral education from departments one that it was because of formed moral culture (or really spirituality) a lot

in terms of exactly communication in culture and that's it with together himself manifestation does. Communication culture, if she is a person outlook based on moral to values if it is not justified, it does not become a natural continuation of the personality. We must not forget that communication culture in modern society is a person's value beliefs and behavior character turned, ethics and manners to the rules suitable coming personal important is a unity of worldview relations. Based on this fact, communication formation of culture is understood as a part of the process of moral education it is necessary, here first of all to form behavior and communication skills attention is given but their moral content as well is important.

Many scientists in the last decade communication culture and its formation problems active respectively work came out practical recommendations they gave Communication of the problem different sides AA Boltaboyev [1], IS Con [2], AA Leontiev [3],

ND Tursunov [4], AL Soliyev [5] and others. But this is the analysis of scientific literature showed that non-pedagogical higher study in their countries communication culture directed formation especially is relevant because them study process opportunities, requirements for the organization of educational work, etc. are not used enough, one there is a difference it's not.

All of the above is the problem of forming a culture of communication conditional and specialists preparation quality increase necessity with closely depending on universal, humanity, moral values appropriation and allows to emphasize the necessity of application. Also in direct communication with them done increase not only of young people personal and spiritual development, perhaps of the specialist social, professional to determine the potential help will give [6].

So by doing communication culture understanding people between communication ensuring the progress of the process, in accordance with social norms, unique human behavior own into takes The majority cases communication by itself the goal it's not, perhaps other, communicative didn't happen tasks solution to do is a tool. Communication plays a communicative and mandatory role in collective and group activities of people. Communication content and shape his to the composition entering certain activity with is determined.

It is known that culture to determine the most important mechanism is a language. However, in modern society, it also reflects the fate, thinking and aspirations of the people as a living organism, tolerant relations with representatives of other nations to see it as a means of forming a spiritually rich person who knows how to establish need

Moreover, communication in the process used tools, methods cultureproduct that not to forget need Communication culture communication done to be increased

includes almost all modes of behavior; which shapes speech and which develops words; of speech dynamic features, intonation, gestures, mime, pantomime, etc. - in a word, interpersonal understand and mutually effect which provides tool that acceptance can be done [4].

The role of communication in the formation of personality is very big. Speech communication is all about it forms and in genres to a person previous generations by meaningful and allows you to get a systematized ready-made social experience. Spiritual in communication, intellectual and material culture take over of a person the world and himself to know and as a result of this - the socialization of the individual and the adaptation of human behavior there is. Psychologists stated that adults with oral communication of a person both to master the world around him and to master ways of thinking solution doer important have Oral mutually effect speech communication abilities using done is increased this while own in turn speech in the activity develops and will be improved.

So, communication is a very complex and multifaceted process, which is covered by different disciplines representatives - philosophers, sociologists, cultural studies, psychologists and linguists they learn. Philosophers of communication a person and society in his life place _ a person in development role they learn. Sociologists different social groups and groups between communication shapes, social reasons with depends communication of types learn the differences. Psychologists study both the form of activity and human behavior, individual psychotypical characteristics of communication, as well as individual communication mind in the structure place seeing they come out. Cultural scholars culture types and contact forms between relationships they install. Linguists social and linguistic and interpersonal communication speech learn the

nature.

Summary by doing so to speak modern society conditions of the person communication culture the problem to understand for transition period of society features, his change forms and the future for forecasts analysis who does things learning big is important.

So, summarizing what has been said, we have a high communication culture we come to the conclusion that students should have the following knowledge can:

- of a person psychological features;
- in communication psychological tights _ and them eliminate reach ways;
- manners rules;
- behavior of culture basics;
- speech of culture basics;
- external view of culture basics;
- contact basics.

Also below skills our formation condition:

- ✓ communicative activity organize reach;
- ✓ contact processes in order put
- ✓ listen and understand;
- ✓ contact installation;
- ✓ own your opinion to notify;
- ✓ to others meaningful speech based on effect to do and of them study;
- ✓ another of the person psychological to the situation and his behavior adequateto answer;
- ✓ belongs to contact shape choose;
- ✓ himself and others analysis to do and evaluate;
- ✓ modern in society that's right communication to do learning and

others.

CONCLUSION

So, communication culture and its characteristics in modern society are social reflected in language phenomena . Acceptance of language as a means of communication social and cultural life of the countries and peoples who speak this language learning duties with organic is connected.

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